

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

PEDAGOGICAL-PROGRAMM IMPLEMENTATION OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF ENVIRONMENTAL EDUCATION IN HIGHER CLASS PUPILS OF SECONDARY SCHOOLS

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Annotation. This article discusses the use of software to improve students' environmental education skills and mechanisms. Improving the quality and content of online resources, focusing on the number and quality of educational platforms, the implementation of algorithms and modules. The development of computer skills in students during the period of scientific and technological development requires special attention to the issues of adaptation to the educational process.

Keywords: environmental education, environmental awareness, social education, software, animation, model, environmental issues

Introduction. Improving the content of modern forms of environmental education in general secondary schools is a modern requirement. The development of science and technology and the development of modern computer networks today demand that the issues of enriching the content of science programs, the development of social consciousness, the achievement of harmony in the relationship with nature and society remain relevant.

The factor of human development, the development of science and technology has raised the relationship between society and nature to the next level. Raising the level of human attitude to nature, environmental awareness and culture, the use of modern technology in improving the mechanisms of environmental education is of great importance as an important issue today. Such decisions as the day-to-day development of young people's skills in the use of various techniques and technologies, proper organization of their leisure time, proper use of Internet resources, increasing the number of scientific portals in the field of education and upbringing and similar issues are regulated in Presidential Decree PF-6079 of 5.10.2020 and the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of December 31, 2019 No 265 "On approval of the concept of continuous spiritual education and measures to implement it", PF-60 dated 28.01.2022. Particular attention is paid to the use of software, increase the number of electronic resources and portals, increase the quantity and quality of educational platforms. At present, the competence of young people in the use of computer technology is growing day by day. On the one hand, the breadth of the virtual world, the abundance of opportunities to use it, the reduction

of time and costs, on the other hand, to ensure that the younger generation is not too tightly connected to the spider web, properly organize their free time, pay attention to the content and quality of Internet portals. An important issue facing our state is to increase the resources that contain the materials that form the basis of moral and social education.

Relevance of the topic. As society has evolved, environmental problems have also evolved day by day and have become global problems that need to be addressed by humanity. The development of skills such as love of nature, creating a healthy environment, preserving the diversity of the components of nature plays a key role in shaping the attitude of today's young generation to nature. Software tools have many conveniences to use, saving time and resources, costs. Online platforms and resources differ from other resources by their ease of operation, consistency, and ease of obtaining data at any time.

At present, the development of technical, technological and software competencies among young people raises the issue of improving the online resources used by students, enriching the content, improving the resources used by students and youth. What portals do young people work with? What do they spend their free time on? What is the share of educational resources in online resources? How much time do young people spend in entertainment programs and networks? These issues are very topical. After all, today our young people spend a lot of time on social networks and entertainment programs. Improving the weight, content and quality of online resources in improving the skills of spiritual, moral and social

education remains one of the main challenges of today.

The purpose of the study. The purpose of the study is to improve the mechanisms of environmental education in software tools. There is a great demand today for the development of environmental education skills in students using online resources in education, modern software tools. Improving the quality of students' Internet access through mobile applications, online resources and platforms, increasing the competence of socio-environmental education and contributing to the meaningful organization of leisure time of young people.

Improving the mechanisms of modern socio-environmental education in software currently sets the following requirements:

- Development of social education skills in students;
- Improving the competence of working with information technology;
- Ability to apply modern teaching methods in the classroom;
- Ability to use technical software to improve the mechanisms of social education;
- Creation and improvement of databases that develop environmental education skills in the system of information and communication networks;
- Improving the quality of resources that serve to improve the mechanisms of environmental education, ease, convenience, speed in data sorting, achieving data reliability and accuracy, etc.

Research hypothesis. Identify features of improving the mechanisms of environmental education using technical and technological capabilities in improving the mechanisms of social education, including environmental education. Adequate approach to the environment can be developed in young people through the development and implementation of indicators of self-monitoring, analysis, understanding, evaluation.

- Scientific and theoretical analysis of the improvement of environmental education mechanisms in software, study of ways to increase their effectiveness;

- Determining the indicators of environmental education and the level of assessment;
- Determining the level of environmental education;
- Development of a model for monitoring the process of environmental education;

The purpose of improving the mechanisms of environmental education in software: In improving the mechanisms of environmental education, we must pay attention to the development of the following features in students:

- Teaching to imagine eco-images, to understand problems, to love and care for nature;
- Development of skills in understanding, imagining environmental problems, describing environmental problems, creating algorithms for nature conservation through software;
- Ability to see environmental problems, to understand the cause-and-effect factors, to analyze, to express an opinion on the problem and to develop the ability to describe it in algorithms and models.

Analysis and methodology of scientific literature on the topic. The history of ecological teachings dates back to ancient times. Examples include works by Aristotle, famous Indian epics, and the Avesta. With the development of human thinking and consciousness, the development of religious and secular teachings, the emphasis on environmental education has also developed. Well-known educator Jan Amos Comenius highlighted the role of nature in the education of man in his work "The Great Didactics".¹ Jan Comenius advocated that the processes in society are related to nature, that nature is created on the basis of certain laws, and that the principle of education is in harmony with nature, that man is part of nature and that he is part of nature subject to its most basic, general laws. According to Jan Comenius, these laws of nature also have an effect on the plant and animal kingdoms, and man, as a part of nature and as a part of nature, is subject to its most basic, general laws.² These laws of nature have an effect on the plant and animal world, as well as on man. According to Jean-Jacques Russo,

¹ https://sinref.ru/000_uchebniki/03800pedagog/000_lekcii_pedagog_01/004.htm

² <https://bank.nauchniestati.ru/primery/doklad-na-temu-ekologicheskoe-obrazovanie-v-pedagogicheskoy-nauke/>

children should be brought up naturally in accordance with nature. He believes that children get their upbringing from three sources: nature, the people and things around them.³

The issue of pedagogical foundations of environmental education was discussed by academician I.D. Zverev (Fundamentals of Ecological Theory)⁴, AN Zakhlebniy (Pedagogical Foundations of Ecological Education)⁵, E.O. Turdikulov (Problems of providing with ecological education in teaching natural sciences)⁶, I. Suravegina (Providing with ecological education in teaching Biology)⁷ and reflected in the research work of a number of scientists.

Problem statement: In order to increase the competence of modern environmental education, it is necessary to pay attention to a number of requirements. In addition to improving the mechanisms of environmental education, it is important to direct students to environmental research activities. It is very important to develop skills such as generating ideas and concepts about ecosystems and the natural environment, understanding the process, evaluating, expressing opinions, and observing.

Software has to apply software code and algorithms in practice to implement an idea in the field of computer science. Increasing the role and importance of software in the development and improvement of environmental education skills in secondary schools is directly related to the development of technical and technological competence of students. Implementation of environmental education mechanisms in software means the implementation of ideas to improve the mechanisms of education through software.

In the development of ecological consciousness and culture, first of all, it is necessary to help the student to think correctly about the components of nature and events in nature, that man is a part of nature, to analyze the ecological situation. The student should be able to monitor the nature of their habitat, gather knowledge about natural-archaeological-

recreational protected areas, develop knowledge, skills and competencies in environmental monitoring.

We are assisted by the programs "ecalendar", "agenda", "daily observations", "eco-sticker", "ecologos", which are part of the online platform. These programs are very convenient for setting the agenda, planning and conducting environmental monitoring, checking the progress of environmental monitoring, and also help students to organize their free time properly. The ecological calendar includes information on nature protection, nature holidays and important dates. The agenda includes information on the structure of the content of daily activities. Eco-sticker and Ecologos programs can be used for fun games for young schoolchildren and game-related answers, questions and answers, creative puzzles. It is expedient to start the implementation of environmental education mechanisms with the development of software tools and simple algorithms. Simple animations, simple algorithms, slides and sequences serve to improve the mechanisms of environmental education in students.

Why use animation software in education and upbringing? First of all, to develop new skills in students. Animation is a universal tool that develops working skills in students, as well as in animation programs the student understands better because of his direct participation, new creative ideas emerge. From this point of view, the student first of all understands what he can do in the programs he works on, understands the essence of the content.

Let's take a look at the advantages of Blender animation software - one of the simplest animation programs that students can do. Blender⁸ is a 3D animation program that makes it much easier to create educational animated presentations and clips. Blender features - displays excellent animations based on the tracking mechanism, can preview the live screen, has a range that supports high-definition lighting, a complete set of

³ https://xn--j1ahfl.xn--p1ai/library/osnovnie_pedagogicheskie_idei_zhanzhaka_russso_201520.html

⁴ Зверев И.Д. Экология в школьном образовании. Новый аспект образования.- М.: Знание, 1980. 96 с.

⁵ Захлебный А.Н. Принципы и условия экологического образования в школе/Педагогические принципы и

условия экологического образования: Сб. науч.тр — М.: 1983.- С. 10-15

⁶ Турдикулов Э.О. Атроф мухит ва инсон. – Т.: Биоэкосан, 1996. – 28 б

⁷ Суравегина И.Т. Экология для учителя. М.: Издательский дом. 1999.-132 с.

⁸ <https://filmora.wondershare.com/ru/animated-video/best-3d-animation-software-free-paid.html>

modeling tools, 3D drawing, painting, easy and convenient texting.

Let's take a look at a series of animations to interpret the environmental situation that occurs due to deforestation. First of all, the animation is created by depicting a lush green area with trees, gradually showing the process of tree felling and desertification, and in the next stage by showing desert and barren soils, an area that has become waterless and arid due to tree felling. In this animation, images of trees and their cuttings are created by placing and painting, illustrating in sequence. When the reader creates this animation, he understands and thinks about how to interact with nature through these processes, improves his understanding of how to properly relate human relationships with nature, develops creative thinking.

Key analysis and results: It is necessary to develop work in such areas as "mini-games", "eco-calendar", "eco-reminder", "did you know?", "Red book", which form and develop environmental education skills through simple and easy programs that are part of online platforms and resources. Information on holidays and days on an environmental theme related to special dates can be planned and executed through special applications on smartphones and tablets. For example, in the "Red Book" and "Did you know" sections, you can enter data into the online program, create such things.

March 21 – Navruz holiday or International Forest Day, April 15 – Environmental Awareness Day, May 3 – Sun Day, October 4 – World Animal Day.⁹ Here are some examples of questions from the Red Book: What is the Red Book? What plants and animals are listed in the Red Book? What are the flora and fauna? questions such as We have summarized the results as a result of a number of studies and discussions on improving the mechanisms of environmental education in software.

When we ask young people with computer skills questions about robotics, most of them say that in the future there are plans to create devices or robots that will clean the surrounding area, collect garbage and sort it. When we ask high

school students what they think about environmental measures, they point out that environmental protection and conservation should increase fines, sort trash cans by color and teach children from an early age to dump in a designated box, and promote tree planting. In the "Man and Nature" drawing competition, the majority of students expressed their opposition to deforestation, saying that deforestation is causing global warming and dust storms.

Conclusion: In conclusion, we can say that at the present time, technical and technological progress is growing rapidly, and at the same time the issues of improving the mechanisms of environmental education are becoming increasingly important. Observing nature, the events that take place in it - the development of students' skills of understanding events, expressing ideas, imagining images and modeling them - these are the problems of today.

- Enrichment of Internet resources used by young people in terms of quality and weight;
- Pay attention to the content and essence of the resources used;
- Pay attention to the spiritual, educational and social analysis of the content;
- Planning and programming the proper organization of youth leisure;
- It is necessary to take into account the issues of collecting, generalizing environmental knowledge, the correct use of this knowledge and information in relation to the environment, and data modeling.

Childhood is a period of rapid development of the child. The environment is an important stage in the formation of an intensive relationship with the world and nature in which we live, especially in the middle and upper grades of school age. It is important to improve the skills of environmental education of young people in accordance with modern technologies, the rational use and intensive reproduction of natural resources, the development of environmental culture in connection with nature and society.

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⁹ Electronic Ecological Library:
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